

SmartCHP
COGENERATING A RENEWABLE FUTURE

D.2.4

The production of FPBO from selected feedstock

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Authors	Evert Leijenhorst
Reviewers	Bert van de Beld
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Publishable summary

Fast Pyrolysis Bio Oil (FPBO) can be produced from a variety of lignocellulosic biomass materials. In this report the results are presented concerning the production of FPBO from the biomass feedstocks selected in the SmartCHP project. The FPBOs are used within the project for further development work of the SmartCHP system. Detailed analysis results for the FPBOs are reported in deliverables 2.6, 2.7 and 2.8. Important properties such as heating value and moisture content are included in this report as well to derive mass, energy and carbon balances and ensure this report can be read without consulting the other (non-public) reports.

The biomass selection is based on availability, suitability and sustainability and is reported in detail in deliverable 2.2. Five scenarios are made covering four different biomass materials and one import scenario:

- Agricultural residues – corn stover - Romania
- Organic waste – olive kernel - Greece
- Woody biomass – forest residue – Sweden
- FPBO import scenario – Sweden to the Netherlands
- Dedicated bioenergy crop – miscanthus - Croatia

Conform the grant agreement, three biomass materials were selected and supplied by Capax for conversion to FPBO in BTGs bench-scale pyrolysis plant. For the fourth material (miscanthus) previous tests have been performed at BTG and sufficient information is already available as input for the scenario studies. FPBO produced from miscanthus is also available for testing.

The results from the experimental work showed that each of the materials could be processed in the bench-scale pyrolysis plant without operational problems. The FPBO production results show that the wood residues generate the highest FPBO yield (68 wt.%) followed by corn stover (56% wt.%) and olive kernels (49 wt.%). The FPBO derived from wood residues was a single-phase homogeneous liquid. Both corn stover and olive kernel derived FPBO consisted of an aqueous phase and an organic phase which needed to be conditioned (partial water removal) to generate a homogeneous liquid.

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1. Introduction

Biomass can be converted by fast pyrolysis to form a liquid product called Fast Pyrolysis Bio-Oil (FPBO). FPBO is recognized as a 2nd generation or advanced biofuel/intermediate energy carrier. The production of FPBO is recently commercialized with the construction and operation of the first plants in Europe.

At the moment, three plants are in operation and a fourth under construction. Each of these plants uses wood residues as biomass feedstock. Use of woody biomass leads to a high liquid yield and a good quality product. The conversion of other biomass residues, especially agricultural residues and organic wastes can lead to a lower liquid yield and an inferior quality product. However, agricultural residues and organic wastes are potentially lower-value feedstocks which could improve the economic feasibility of FPBO production.

In this report, results are presented on the conversion of three biomass materials to investigate the process performance and determine the aftertreatment necessary to obtain a quality suitable for use in the SmartCHP system.

Specifically, woody (sawmill) residues are selected as a resource available in Sweden. This material is known to produce a good quality FPBO in good yields and will serve as a good reference case in the project.

Corn stover is an agricultural residue which remains after corn is cultivated and harvested for human consumption.

Olive kernel is a waste/residue from food production (primarily olive oil) in Southern Europe.

2. Materials and methods

This chapter describes the materials and methods used for the FPBO production

2.1 Materials

The biomass materials used for FPBO production were supplied by Capax and delivered as much as possible 'on spec' for direct conversion to FPBO. For the fast pyrolysis process, the most important properties are the moisture content and particle size. The moisture content of the biomass is important because all moisture contained in the biomass will end up in the FPBO product. When the moisture content exceeds a certain threshold (typically around 25 wt.%) phase separation will occur, in practice the moisture content of the biomass should be below 10 wt.% and preferably below 5 wt.% before feeding it to the reactor. The particle size is important because the process relies on fast heating rates to optimize the liquid yield. The heat conductivity resistance for particles larger than typically 5-10 mm are known to limit FPBO yield.

2.1.1 Wood residues

The selected wood residues were obtained from a sawmill in Sweden, where the material is dried, pelletized and crumbled to achieve the desired specifications. This route was chosen to improve transport and also allow for a better feed properties in the bench-scale pyrolysis plant. In a commercial scenario, the pyrolysis plant would be located next to the sawmill and only drying would be required.

In Fig. 1 a photograph of the wood residues as supplied by Capax can be seen. The analysis results of this material are presented in Table 1, together with the other biomass materials.

Fig. 1: Photograph of the wood residues used for FPBO production

2.1.2 Corn stover

The corn stover was delivered by Capax in dried-pelletized form. The pellets were crumbeled by BTG (see 2.2.1) to achieve the desired particle size. A photograph of the original pellets and the crumbeled material as fed to the reactor is presented in Fig. 2, the analysis results are presented in table 1.

Fig. 2: Photograph of the corn stover pellets (left) and crumbeled material used for FPBO production.

2.1.3 Olive kernel

Olive kernel was selected as an organic waste material from food processing industry. The composition of the residue depends on the harvesting and processing systems. After the initial press of the olives (yielding extra virgin olive oil) quite some olive-oil remains in the residue (referred to as pomace). This olive-oil can be extracted in multiple steps yielding so called olive pomace oil. After extraction the pit/stone from the olives can be separated from the residue if desired. The pit/stone has a higher energy density and is sometimes used for energy supply in the processing system. In Greece the separation is often not performed because of the limited economic feasibility, and the residue is sold/destroyed including the pit/stone. The material supplied by Capax is the olive residue after extraction, including pit/stone. A photograph is presented in Fig 3, analysis results in Table 1.

Fig. 3: Photograph of the olive kernel in the dryer before FPBO production.

2.1.4 Composition of the biomass materials

The composition of the biomass materials, as fed to the reactor, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Analysis results of the biomass materials.

	unit	Wood residue	Corn Stover	Olive kernel
EA (a.r.)				
C	[wt%]	48.9	46.7	50.9
H	[wt%]	6.2	6.0	6.0
N	[wt%]	0.05	1.1	1.1
Water content	[wt%]	4.9	3.0	1.5
Ash content (A.R)	[wt%]	0.2	2.7	5.03
LHV (a.r)	[MJ/kg]	17.1	16.6	19.0

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Pretreatment

Ensuring the biomass feedstock has a low moisture content and small particle size are critical in the pyrolysis process. Capax supplied the feedstocks as much as possible to the desired specifications, however for the quantities required in this work (~100 kg) it's challenging to arrange the required pretreating at reasonable cost. In agreement with BTG, in some cases minor treatment was performed at BTG, which is shortly described here.

The wood residues were delivered according to specifications and used without further aftertreatment.

The corn stover was delivered in pelletized form. BTG crumbled the pellets using a crumbling machine consisting of two rotating metal rolls with a small gap in between, which is normally used for grain crushing. The moisture content was reduced from approx. 10 wt.% upon delivery to ~3 wt.% for pyrolysis processing by batch-wise drying with hot-air (~80 °C).

The olive kernel particle size was according to specifications upon delivery, the moisture content was reduced from approx. 10 wt.% using the same dryer as the corn stover, resulting in a moisture content of 1.5 wt.% before pyrolysis.

2.2.2 Fast pyrolysis

The biomass materials are converted in BTG's bench-scale pyrolysis plant. This facility has a maximum capacity around 5 kg/h and is typically operated in daytime runs to produce ~5kg of FPBO. Analyses are performed on feedstock, liquid, solid and gaseous products to achieve a full mass, energy, and carbon balance.

In Fig. 4 a schematic representation of the bench-scale plant is presented. The setup is designed according to BTG's patented pyrolysis concept. The biomass is mixed with hot sand in the reactor to initiate the pyrolysis reactions. The char by-product from the reaction leaves the reactor together with the cooled down sand stream. This mixture is fed to the char combustor, where the char is combusted with a surplus amount of air. These combustion reactions re-heat the sand, after which it is transported to the pyrolysis reactor again. The organic vapour and pyrolysis gases leave the reactor through a second opening and flow via two cyclones to the condenser section. In the first condenser, most of the organic vapour is condensed through direct contact with circulating pyrolysis oil. Here, approximately 95% of the total liquid product is obtained. For improved balance closure, a second and third condenser (not shown in the figure) are included. The composition and volume flow of the non-condensable gas is measured periodically to determine the pyrolysis gas production.

Fig. 4: Schematic representation of the bench-scale pyrolysis plant.

For each of the biomass materials, multiple tests (minimum 2) were performed to determine the mass, energy, and carbon balance and to produce sufficient FPBO for further testing. For the first test with each feedstock, 'isopar¹' was used as 'pyrolysis oil insoluble' start-up liquid. After the test the pyrolysis oil and isopar phases were separated. For the second test in the series, pyrolysis oil from the first test is used as start-up liquid. In case the product from the first test is phase-separated, some conditioning work (water removal by evaporation) is performed to ensure a homogeneous start-up liquid is used. To avoid contaminations, the system was thoroughly cleaned before each test and fresh (unused) sand was used as heat carrier material.

3. Results and discussion

In this chapter the results of the FPBO production is presented for each of the feedstocks. A complete overview of the results is added as appendix 1.

3.1 Wood residues

Two separate tests were performed using the wood residues. The material could be processed without operational problems using the standard operating conditions. The average results for the different biomass materials are included in the same tables (paragraph 3.4) to obtain a direct comparison. In Table 2 the mass balance is presented on as received basis and in Table 3 on dry ash free basis. The latter is a better way to represent the conversion of the organic matter from the biomass to the actual products. The carbon balance is presented in Table 4, the energy balance in Table 5.

The only aftertreatment performed on the wood-residue derived FPBO involved filtration to remove the solids.

3.2 Corn stover

Two separate tests were performed with the corn stover as well. After production the FPBO from the first test was phase-separated into an aqueous phase and an organic phase. Both were separated and analysed separately. After analysis the phases were combined in a rotavapor to remove part of the water in order to have a homogenous liquid as start-up liquid for the second test. The second test with corn stover resulted in a relatively poor balance closure with a notably lower organic liquid yield (26% versus 37% in the first test). Therefore, only the results from the first test are used in evaluating the different scenarios. The full experimental results are included in the appendix.

The operating conditions were similar to the wood residues and no operational problems were encountered. The results from the first test with corn stover are presented in Table 2 (a.r. mass balance), Table 3 (dry ash free balance), Table 4 (carbon balance) and Table 5 (energy balance).

The corn stover FPBO was conditioned by vacuum evaporation to remove part of the water and obtain a homogeneous liquid. Also, the FPBO was filtered to remove the solids.

3.3 Olive kernel

For the olive kernel the second test had to be terminated due to increased pressure drop over the reactor, caused by contaminations in the vapour line. The build-up of contaminations is sometimes observed when fine biomass/char particles are entrained from the reactor and insufficiently removed by the cyclones. This can be avoided by a further optimization of the feed capacity to the reactor and is not considered an operational problem for commercial implementation. Because of the difficulties during the second test, a third run was performed to have sufficient FPBO for the project. For the first two tests the products were analysed to obtain the information required to derive the mass, energy, and carbon balance. The third test was 'production only' and no product analysis was made.

The operating conditions were similar to the wood residues and corn stover, only the biomass feed rate was slightly higher at 3.3 kg/h versus 2.6 kg/h for the wood residues and 2.8 kg/h for the corn stover. The average results for the first two tests with olive kernel are presented in Table 2 (a.r. mass balance), Table 3 (dry ash free balance), Table 4 (carbon balance) and Table 5 (energy balance).

The olive kernel FPBO was conditioned by vacuum evaporation to remove part of the moisture and obtain a homogeneous liquid. Also, the FPBO was filtered to remove the solids.

3.4 Overview of the results

Table 2: Mass balance for FPBO production from the biomass materials on as received basis.

a.r. balance	unit	Wood residue	Corn Stover	Olive kernel
Liquid yield	[wt%]	68%	56%	49%
Gas yield	[wt%]	21%	23%	22%
Char yield	[wt%]	18%	17%	21%
Ash recovery	[wt%]	0.2%	2.7%	5.0%
Balance closure	[wt%]	106%	98%	97%

Table 3: Mass balance for FPBO production from the biomass materials on dry ash free basis.

d.a.f. balance	unit	Wood residue	Corn Stover	Olive kernel
Organic liquid	[wt%]	55%	37%	33%
Water production	[wt%]	7%	21%	18%
Gas production	[wt%]	22%	24%	24%
Char production	[wt%]	19%	18%	23%
Balance closure	[wt%]	102%	99%	97%

Table 4: Carbon balance for FPBO production from the biomass materials

Carbon balance	unit	Wood residue	Corn Stover	Olive kernel
Carbon to liquid	[wt%]	63%	46%	42%
Carbon to gas	[wt%]	17%	18%	16%
Carbon to char	[wt%]	30%	30%	34%
Carbon balance closure	[wt%]	110%	94%	92%

Table 5: Energy recovery for FPBO production from the biomass materials

Energy recovery	unit	Wood residue	Corn Stover	Olive kernel
Energy recovery in liquid	[J/J]	0.66	0.48	0.44
Energy recovery in gas	[J/J]	0.11	0.08	0.08
Energy recovery in char	[J/J]	0.30	0.32	0.34
Total energy to products	[J/J]	1.08	0.88	0.86

4. Conclusions

The selected feedstock could be converted to FPBO without operational problems. As expected, the FPBO yield was highest for the wood residue feedstock (68%). Both corn-stover (56%) and olive kernels (49%) resulted in a lower FPBO yield. Through optimization of the process conditions the reported yield can likely be improved a somewhat but yields close to that of wood residues are unlikely.

The FPBO produced from corn stover and olive kernels both consisted of two phases, an organic rich fraction, and an aqueous fraction. Removing part of the water (and light organics) by vacuum evaporation was a suitable way to ensure a homogenous liquid is produced. In a commercial production facility, the vacuum evaporation will be added directly to the FPBO production site and sufficient energy is available from the plant for the evaporation process.

Appendix: detailed experimental results

	Wood residue 1	Wood residue 2	Olive kernel 1	Olive kernel 2	Olive kernel 3 (extra production)	Corn Stover 1	Corn Stover 2
Input							
Temperature [°C]	500	496	510	514	509	502	497
Runtime [h]	2	2	2,0	1,5	3,2	2	2
Feedrate (a.r.) [kg/h]	2,7	2,4	3,2	3,3	3,4	2,8	2,8
Massbance (a.r.)							
Liquid production [wt.%]	70%	66%	48%	50%	50%	56%	53%
Gas production [wt.%]	21%	20%	22%	23%	23%	23%	22%
Kool production [wt.%]	17%	18%	21%	22%	24%	17%	16%
As 'production' [wt.%]	0,20%	0,20%	5%	5%	5%	2,70%	2,70%
Balance closure [wt.%]	108%	104%	96%	99%	101%	98%	94%
Massbalance (d.a.f.)							
Organische liquid [wt.%]	58%	52%	30%	35%		37%	26%
Water production [wt.%]	6%	8%	20%	16%		21%	27%
Gas production [wt.%]	22%	21%	23%	24%		24%	23%
Char production [wt.%]	18%	19%	22%	23%		18%	17%
Balance closure [wt.%]	104%	100%	95%	98%		99%	94%

	Wood residue 1	Wood residue 2		Olive kernel 1	Olive kernel 2	Olive kernel 3 (extra production)		Corn Stover 1	Corn Stover 2
Elemental balance									
Carbon to liquid	65%	61%		42%	43%			46%	46%
Carbon to gas	18%	17%		15%	16%			18%	17%
Carbon to char	29%	31%		33%	35%			30%	28%
Carbon recovery	112%	109%		90%	94%			94%	90%
Energy balance									
Energy to liquid	68%	65%		44%	44%			48%	20%
Energy to char	30%	30%		33%	35%			32%	28%
Energy to gas	11%	11%		8%	9%			8%	8%
Energy recovery	109%	106%		85%	88%			88%	56%

	Wood residue 1	Wood residue 2	Olive kernel 1	Olive kernel 2	Olive kernel 3 (extra production)	Corn Stover 1	Corn Stover 2
Analysis results							
Biomass							
H2O (a.r) [wt.%]	4,70%	5,00%	1,20%	1,30%	1,80%	3,00%	3,00%
Ash (dry) [wt.%]	0,20%	0,20%	5,03%	5,03%	5,03%	2,69%	2,69%
C (dry) [wt.%]	48,88%	48,88%	50,85%	50,85%	50,85%	46,70%	46,70%
H (dry) [wt.%]	6,17%	6,17%	6,00%	6,00%	6,00%	6,00%	6,00%
N (dry) [wt.%]	0,05%	0,05%	1,12%	1,12%	1,12%	1,10%	1,10%
O (dry, by diff) [wt.%]	44,70%	44,70%	37,00%	37,00%	37,00%	43,51%	43,51%
LHV [MJ/kg]	17,1	17,1	19,1	19,03	18,92	16,6	16,6
Char							
Ash (dry) [wt.%]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
C (dry) [wt.%]	78,30%	79,26%	79,88%	80,47%		80,76%	77,86%
H (dry) [wt.%]	4,86%	3,48%	4,24%	4,38%		5,04%	4,40%
N (dry) [wt.%]	1,00%	0,80%	2,58%	2,31%		2,79%	1,72%
O (dry, by diff) [wt.%]	15,84%	16,46%	13,29%	12,84%		11,42%	16,02%
LHV [MJ/kg]	30,04	28,8	30,01	30,46		31,4	29,28
Organic phase [wt.% total liquid]							
H2O (a.r) [wt.%]	25,44%	25,11%	24,51%	8,97%	48,10%	16,63%	13,02%
C (a.r.) [wt.%]	43,54%	43,23%	61,22%	63,62%		56,09%	59,13%
H (a.r.) [wt.%]	7,78%	8,09%	8,80%	7,47%		8,20%	8,00%
N (a.r.) [wt.%]	0,70%	0,37%	2,32%	2,50%		2,15%	4,30%
O (a.r., by diff) [wt.%]	47,98%	48,32%	27,64%	26,41%		33,56%	28,57%
LHV [MJ/kg]	16,57	16,82	26,0	26,11		23,22	24,52%

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	Wood residue 1	Wood residue 2	Olive kernel 1	Olive kernel 2	Olive kernel 3 (extra production)	Corn Stover 1	Corn Stover 2
Waterphase [wt.% total liq]			41,75%	42,65%	51,90%	63,40%	64%
H2O (a.r) [wt.%]			65,14%	66,39%		51,43%	46,97%
C (a.r.) [wt.%]			17,89%	16,34%		26,50%	28,05%
H (a.r.) [wt.%]			9,51%	9,86%		8,83%	8,83%
N (a.r.) [wt.%]			1,25%	1%		0,74%	0,86%
O (a.r., by diff) [wt.%]			71,63%	72,80%		63,93%	62,26%
LHV [MJ/kg]			5,3	4,92		8,94	9,84
Gas production (N2 free)							
CH4 [wt.%]	3,50%	4,20%	5,01%	5,19%	4,78%	2,69%	2,49%
CO [wt.%]	44,70%	43,25%	20,33%	20,92%	21,38%	26,60%	26,70%
CO2 [wt.%]	46,10%	46,88%	68,57%	68,82%	69,68%	67,05%	67,17%
C2+ [wt.%]	5,70%	5,62%	6,09%	5,07%	4,16%	3,66%	3,64%
LHV [MJ/kg]	9,28	9,45	7,09	7,23	6,66	5,93	5,83
Gas wt.%							
C	39,15%	39,23%	35,68%	35,84%	35,22%	34,75%	34,65%
H	1,81%	1,97%	2,12%	2,16%	1,91%	1,29%	1,24%
O	59,06%	58,83%	62,22%	62,02%	62,89%	63,98%	64,13%

